

1 Complete description of the skull and mandible of the giant mustelid *Eomellivora*
2 *piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965 (Mammalia, Carnivora, Mustelidae) from Batallones
3 (MN10), Late Miocene (Madrid, Spain)

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3 27 RH: VALENCIANO ET AL.—*SKULL OF EOMELLIVORA FROM*

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5 28 *BATALLONES*

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12 33 ABSTRACT—We describe cranial, mandibular and dental remains of five

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14 34 individuals of the giant mustelid *Eomellivora piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965 from the

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16 35 late Miocene (MN10) site of Cerro de los Batallones, (Madrid, Spain) – the first

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18 36 complete cranial remains recorded for this species and the most complete remains

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20 37 of the genus. This new sample enables a review the systematic status of

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22 38 *Eomellivora* leading us to accept as valid species *E. piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965, *E.*

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24 39 *wimani* Zdansky, 1924, *E. ursogulo* (Orlov, 1948) and *E. hungarica* Kretzoi, 1942.

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26 40 Our phylogenetic hypothesis indicates that *Eomellivora* is the sister taxon of the

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28 41 extant *Mellivora capensis* and *E. piveteaui* had a common ancestor with the crown

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30 42 group *E. wimani*-*E. ursogulo*. *Eomellivora piveteaui* was adapted to a more

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32 43 hypercarnivorous diet than the largest extant terrestrial mustelids though it also had

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34 44 some derived bone-crushing adaptations. *Eomellivora piveteaui* had an active

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36 45 predatory role in the Late Miocene Carnivore faunas, exploiting both small and

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38 46 relatively large preys.

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42 48 INTRODUCTION

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46 50 The Cerro de los Batallones fossil sites (Late Miocene [MN10]) have yielded

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48 51 some of the most interesting, richest and best-preserved Neogene mammal

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50 52 assemblages of the Iberian Peninsula (Morales et al., 2008). It is a system of nine

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52 53 distinct sites located on a structural butte in the south of the province of Madrid,

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3 54 Spain (Fig. 1). Fossil remains indicate a Late Vallesian age (ca 9 Ma), for all the
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5 55 sites. However, there are slight differences in composition in micro- and
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7 56 macromammals among the different fossil deposits that have been attributed to
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9 57 minor temporal differences indicating, for instance, that Batallones-10 is older than
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11 58 Batallones-3 (López-Antoñanzas et al., 2010; Siliceo et al., 2014). All these
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13 59 Batallones sites were cavities that acted as natural traps for vertebrates. The
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15 60 fossiliferous deposits are embedded in marls and are composed of two types of
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17 61 assemblages: (1) subsurface cavities (e.g. Batallones-1 and Batallones-3)
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19 62 interpreted as carnivore traps and (2) doline-like depressions (e.g. Batallones-4 and
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21 63 Batallones-10) interpreted as herbivore traps. Both types differ in their stratigraphic
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23 64 relative position, internal stratigraphic architecture, taxonomic composition and
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25 65 taphonomic features (Pozo et al., 2004, Morales et al., 2008; Abella, 2011; Abella
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27 66 et al., 2011, Domingo et al., 2011, 2013; Calvo et al., 2013).

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31 67 The numerous excavation campaigns in the different Batallones localities
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33 68 have yielded a rich assemblage of vertebrate fossils including, fishes, amphibians,
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35 69 reptiles (small and giant tortoises, lizards), and predatory birds (Morales et al.,
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37 70 2008; Pérez-García and Murelaga., 2013), as well as micromammals (López-
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39 71 Antoñanzas et. al., 2010), herbivores (Morales et al., 2008; Sánchez et al., 2009,
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41 72 2011; Ríos et al., 2013) and carnivorans with the latter comprising the most diverse
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43 73 sample (e.g., Antón et al., 2004a, 2004b; Peigné et al., 2005, 2008; Salesa et al.,
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45 74 2006, 2008, 2010, 2012; Abella, 2011; Abella et al., 2011, 2013; Valenciano et al.,
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47 75 2012, 2013).

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51 76 The giant mustelid was identified from Batallones-3 by Valenciano et al.
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53 77 (2012) as *Eomellivora piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965. The richness of this sample is
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55 78 remarkable in that it includes relatively complete cranial and postcranial material,
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3 79 representing the most complete remains known of the genus. The craniodental
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5 80 specimens belong to at least five individuals and include two skulls, eight
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7 81 hemimandibles, and several isolated teeth (Figs. 2–3). *Eomellivora* played an
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9 82 important role in the Late Miocene *Hipparion* faunas, being one of the largest and
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11 83 most hypercarnivorous mustelids ever known, larger and more hypercarnivorous
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13 84 than the extant wolverine, *Gulo gulo* (Valenciano et al., 2013). Eight species of
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15 85 *Eomellivora* have been described from 18 different localities in the Old and New
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17 86 World (e.g. Tobien, 1955; Morlo, 1997; Lupták, 1995; Wolsan and Semenov 1996;
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19 87 Morales and Pickford, 2005; Koufos, 2012), spanning the Middle (MN8) to Late
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21 88 Miocene (MN13). However, Wolsan and Semenov (1996) considered only a single
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23 89 valid species (*E. wimani* Zdansky, 1924), which they subdivided into two
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25 90 chronosubspecies: the Vallesian (MN9–10) *E. w. piveteaui* and the
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27 91 Turolian/Ventian (MN11–13) *E. w. wimani*. The aim of the present paper is to
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29 92 describe in detail the morphology of the complete skull, mandible and dentition of
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31 93 *Eomellivora* from Batallones (including through a 3D digital model that removes
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33 94 some of the taphonomic distortion) and to study the systematic position of
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35 95 *Eomellivora* and its included taxa.
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97 MATERIAL AND METHODS

99 **Nomenclature and Measurements**

100 Dental nomenclature follows Ginsburg (1999) and Smith and Dodson (2003).
101 Anatomical descriptions are based primarily on Scapino (1968), Turnbull (1970),
102 Barone (1999, 2000), Waibl et al. (2005), Evans and de Lahunta (2010, 2013), and
103 Hartstone-Rose et al. (2012). The terminology conforms to the standard of the

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3 104 *Nomina anatomica Veterinaria* (NAV; Waibl et al., 2005) with the exception of the
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5 105 masseter and temporalis muscle complexes for which we follow Hartstone-Rose et
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7 106 al. (2012). We provide a description of the main craniodental features of
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9 107 *Eomellivora* from Batallones, with emphasis on the traits that may indicate its
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11 108 systematic affinities. The Batallones material (Figs. 2–3) has been compared to all
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13 109 the other material of *Eomellivora* on the basis of published descriptions, figures,
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15 110 measurements and photographs (Figs. 4–8) For context, we compared *Eomellivora*
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17 111 to the extant terrestrial mustelids *Eira barbara*, *Gulo gulo*, *Martes martes*,
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19 112 *Mellivora capensis*, and *Pekania pennanti*, as well as the extinct giant mustelids
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21 113 *Ekorus ekakeran*, *Megalictis ferox*, and *Plesiogulo crassa*, described or studied by
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23 114 Matthew (1907), Werdelin (2003), and Koufos (2006). Measurements were made
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25 115 using Mitutoyo Absolute digital calipers to the nearest 0.1 mm (Table 1–2).
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117 **Abbreviations**

118 **Institutional Abbreviations**—AMNH, American Museum of Natural
119 History, New York, USA; **BAT-3**, Batallones-3 locality collection from MNCN;
120 **BAT-10**, Batallones-10 locality collection from MNCN; **IPS**, collection from
121 Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont (ICP), Universitat Autònoma de
122 Barcelona, Spain; **MFGI**, Geological and Geophysical Institute of Hungary,
123 Budapest, Hungary; **MNCN**, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales Madrid,
124 Spain; **MNHN**, Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle, Paris, France; **PIN**,
125 Palaeontological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russia; **PMU**,
126 Palaeontological Museum, University of Uppsala, Uppsala, Sweden; **UST**, Tiraspol
127 State University (Chisinau, Moldova); **VAL**, Anatomical Museum of Valladolid
128 University, Valladolid, Spain.

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6 **130 Studied Material**

7 131 The fossil remains of *E. piveteaui* from Batallones are stored in the
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9 132 collections of the Department of Paleobiología of the MNCN: BAT-3'09.1000 (Fig.
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11 133 2 A1–4, Supplementary Data 1, Figure 1S): skull with P2-M1 and its mandible with
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13 134 p2-m1 (Fig. 3 C); BAT-3'13.185 (Fig. 2 B1–2): skull with P2-M1; BAT-3'09.688
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15 135 (Fig. 2 C1–2): I3; BAT-3'08.635 (Fig. 2 D): C1; BAT-10'08-G4-102 (Fig. 2 E1–3):
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17 136 P2; BAT-3'09.250: P3; BAT-3'09.2b: P4 very worn without protocone; BAT-
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19 137 3'09.2c: lingual half of M1 very worn and without protocone; BAT-3'08.526 (Fig.
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21 138 3 A1–3, Supplementary Data 1, Figure 2S): right hemimandible with c1 and p2-m1;
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23 139 BAT-3'13.230 (Fig. 3 B1–3): left hemimandible with complete ascending ramus,
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25 140 partial p3 and complete p4-m1; BAT-3'12.1086: right hemimandible with complete
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27 141 ascending ramus and partial p4 and m1; BAT-3'09.2: right hemimandible fragment
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29 142 with alveolus for c1 and p1-p4 as well as a very worn m1; BAT-3'11.1180: left
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31 143 hemimandible fragment with p4; BAT-3'09.2a: left hemimandible fragment with
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33 144 m1; BAT-10'12-G2-4 (Fig. 3 D1–8): right hemimandible from juvenile individual
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35 145 with dp4 (Fig. 3 D6–8) and dp3 (Fig. 3 D3–5) as well as m1-m2.
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41 146 The extant specimens used in this paper are from the following collections:

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43 147 *G. gulo* (B.1280) – VAL; *G. gulo* (MNCN-16748), *P. pennati*, *Eira barbara*
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45 148 (MNCN-3727), *Martes martes* (MNCN-3705), *Canis lupus* (MNCN-1968) –
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47 149 MNCN; *Mellivora capensis* (AMNH-51952; AMNH-83450; AMNH-169085) –
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49 150 AMNH.
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54 **152 3-D Model**
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3 153 The skull of *E. piveteaui* from BAT-3 is almost complete, but crushed, due to
4
5 154 the compaction of the sediments resulting in both fragmentation and plastic
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7 155 deformation. This kind of distortion has been previously reported in the carnivoran
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9 156 cranial material from BAT-1 (Domingo et al., 2013). Although the exceptional
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11 157 preservation of the skull permits reliable observations of morphological details, the
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13 158 distortion makes it difficult or impossible to accurately interpret three-dimensional
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15 159 aspects (Antón et al., 2004a). The recovery of the original shape through three-
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17 160 dimensional (3D) reconstruction of individuals with plastic distortions improves
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19 161 overall morphological descriptions, and constitutes a necessary first step toward a
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21 162 correct anatomical reconstruction. Two main deformation forces in BAT-3'09.1000
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23 163 on the sagittal and coronal planes have been detected through observation of the
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25 164 relative position of symmetric structures. A surface 3D model has been obtained
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27 165 using a Next Engine 2020i scanner (Kuzminsky and Gardiner, 2012). In order to
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29 166 restore the original morphology, a shear deformation has been applied to the
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31 167 sagittal plane of the 3D model through the CAD software Autodesk 3D Studio Max
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33 168 with an angle of shearing of 18.3° estimated. Similarly, a 3.4° shearing deformation
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35 169 has been applied to the coronal plane. Both shearing amounts have been estimated
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37 170 based on realignment of paired structures. Although observed, the quantification of
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39 171 the minor dorsoventral distortion is difficult to estimate, thus preventing its
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41 172 correction. The corrected interactive 3D model has been created in PDF 3D format
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43 173 (that can be opened and manipulated in standard PDF viewers) for easy
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45 174 accessibility and comparison (Supplementary Data 1, Figures 1S – 2S).
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SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

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5 179 Order CARNIVORA Bowdich, 1821
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7 180 Suborder CANIFORMIA Kretzoi, 1943
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9 181 Family MUSTELIDAE Fischer von Waldheim, 1817
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11 182 Subfamily MELLIVORINAE Gray, 1865
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13 183 Genus *EOMELLIVORA* Zdansky, 1924
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15 184 *EOMELLIVORA PIVETEAUUI* Ozansoy, 1965
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21 186 *Eomellivora piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965 p1.II, fig.1 (original description).
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23 187 *Eomellivora wimani piveteaui*, Wolsan and Semenov, 1996 (emended diagnosis).
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25 188 **Lectotype**—A partial right mandible with i2-p4 and m1 trigonid, figured by
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27 189 Ozansoy, 1965 p1.II, fig.1 (Wolsan and Semenov, 1996).
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29 190 **Type Locality**—Yassiören (Turkey).
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31 191 **New Localities**—BAT-3 and BAT-10.
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33 192 **Age**—Late Miocene, Early Vallesian MN9 for Yassiören locality (Turkey)
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35 193 (Lunkka et al., 1999), Wissberg locality (Germany) (Tobien, 1955), Kalfa
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37 194 (Moldova)(Lungu and Rzebik-Kowalska, 2011), Los Valles de Fuentidueña (Spain)
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39 195 (Ginsburg et al., 1981); Late Miocene, Late Vallesian MN10 for Batallones
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41 196 localities (Morales et al., 2008) and Ravin de la Plui locality (Greece) (Koufos,
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43 197 2012).
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47 198 **Emended Diagnosis**—Modified after Wolsan and Semenov, (1996). m1
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49 199 talonid with a buccolingually compressed hypoconid, and a small trenchant
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51 200 hypoconulid in line with the protoconid-hypononid. m2 trigonid larger than the
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53 201 talonid; metaconid absent; sharp paraconid, protoconid and hypoconid located
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55 202 along the mesodistal axis.
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3 203 **Differential Diagnosis**—*Eomellivora piveteaui* differs from *E. wimani*, *E.*
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5 204 *ursogulo* and *E. hungarica* in: longer muzzle and more sectorial dentition; reduced
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7 205 p4 mesial accessory cuspid. Additionally, differs from *E. wimani* and *E. ursogulo*
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9 206 in: more slender P2, P4, M1, p2, m2; P2 with a weak lingual cingulum and without
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11 207 cingulum; lingual platform of M1 not enclosed completely the protocone; p3
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13 208 without a buccolingual platform. Differs from *E. wimani* in much more slender P2
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15 209 and p2; less concavity in the buccal wall of P3–P4; P3 with mesial accessory cusp
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17 210 less developed; M1 with more substantial metacone and slender protocone not
18
19 211 centrally located; slender m1 talonid with sharper hypoconid. Differs from *E.*
20
21 212 *ursogulo* in: P3 without two distal accessory cusps; P4 with mesodistally reduced
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23 213 protocone, and without additional cusp in the parastyle; lingual platform of M1
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25 214 without inflexion; p2 without distal accessory cuspid; p3 mesial accessory cuspid
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27 215 not developed and with a much more slender distal area; more primitive m2 with
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29 216 three sharper cuspid in central position along the mesodistal axis. Differs from *E.*
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31 217 *hungarica* in: much longer mandible without reduction of the dental series; p4
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33 218 shorter and more slender, with more vertical main cuspid; m1 more slender and
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35 219 with no lingual cristid.

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43 221 **Description**

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45 222 **Skull and Upper Dentition**— Two skulls (BAT-3'09.1000 and BAT-
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47 223 3'13.185) of *Eomellivora* have been found at Batallones. BAT-3'09.1000 (Fig. 2
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49 224 A1–4) has an approximate basal cranial length of 182.52 mm. Its preservation is
50
51 225 relatively good, despite the fact that it is compressed and warped approximately
52
53 226 18.3° in the sagittal and 3.4° in the coronal planes (Fig. 2). The nuchal and ventral
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55 227 regions are also quite damaged. BAT-3'13.185 (Fig. 2 B1–2) is latero-medially
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3 228 compressed and the nuchal and ventral regions are quite damaged. The foramen
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5 229 magnum, occipital condyles, basisphenoid and basioccipital bones are missing in
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7 230 both specimens. The dentition of BAT-3'09.1000 is partially dissolved by soil
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9 231 acids, and also partially broken with some of the cuspids of the lower teeth being
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11 232 impacted into the upper dentition. The dentition of BAT-3'13.185 is relatively good
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13 233 and retains P2–M1.

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15 234 Based on analysis of both specimens, the Batallones *Eomellivora* skull is
16
17 235 triangular and has a massive aspect in both ventral and dorsal views. It has a
18
19 236 dorsoventrally high snout and the nasal bones are robust and rostrocaudally
20
21 237 developed. The nasal aperture is large and slightly tilted caudally. The frontal
22
23 238 region is weakly domed becoming slightly flat above the orbit (Fig. 2 A3). The
24
25 239 interorbital region is broad. The postorbital processes are marked in BAT-3'13.185.
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27 240 On the maxillary bones there is a moderately deep and rounded fossa in the rostral
28
29 241 margin of the orbit that extends dorsally. The large infraorbital foramen (6.58mm
30
31 242 width and 12.83 mm height in BAT-3'13.185) is located under the frontal process
32
33 243 of the maxilla and above the mesial edge of the P4 paracone. The rostral margin of
34
35 244 the orbit ends at the level of the distal margin of the P4 paracone. BAT-3'09.1000
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37 245 has a weak temporal crest and a well-developed sagittal crest that extends caudally
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39 246 towards the external occipital protuberance, where it divides into the nuchal crests,
40
41 247 forming a Y-pattern. The external occipital protuberance does not exceed the
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43 248 nuchal region. In caudal view (Fig. 2 A4), the nuchal area is triangular, rather flat
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45 249 and has a large area of insertion on the supraoccipital bone.

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47 250 The zygomatic arches are robust in their rostral and caudal areas and are
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49 251 especially robust near the glenoid cavity. Both M. masseter pars superficialis and
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51 252 M. masseter pars profunda have their origin on the ventrolateral side of zygomatic
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3 253 arch. The frontal processes of the zygomatic arches are triangular, high and
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5 254 rostrocaudally broad.

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7 255 Ventrally, the tooth rows are rectilinear between C1–P4. A diastema separates
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9 256 I3–C1. Neither the pterygoid region nor the hamulus pterygoideus processes are
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11 257 well preserved. The tympanic bulla is partially inflated, with a rugose ventral
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13 258 surface and a large and rounded external auditory meatus. The ventral parts of the
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15 259 nuchal crest in conjunction with the mastoid process are well developed and are
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17 260 rostrally widened. The nuchal crest is concave and projects laterally, which
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19 261 creates large attachment areas for *M. zygomatic temporalis* on the dorsal side and
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21 262 *M. obliquus capiti cranialis* on the caudal side. The mastoid process is robust and is
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23 263 situated lateral to the tympanic bulla. The paroccipital process is caudal to the
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25 264 auditory bulla. BAT-3'09.1000 possesses a medium-sized paroccipital process,
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27 265 narrow, triangular in the section and projects laterocaudally. The *M. digastricus*
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29 266 originates on the lateral side of the process.

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34 267 The preserved upper dentition includes the I3, C1, P2, P3, P4 and M1. The I3
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36 268 BAT-3'09.688 (Fig. 2 C1–2) is caniniform with a single cusp curved distally. On
37
38 269 the lingual side there is a sharp crista as well as a marked cingulum. It has a
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40 270 massive root oval in cross-section. The C1 BAT-3'08.635 (Fig. 2 D) has a long and
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42 271 crown, wide at the base. The mesial and distal cristas are corroded. The crown has a
43
44 272 small distal cingulum and the root is robust and buccolingually wide near the
45
46 273 cemento-enamel junction. BAT-3'13.185 has an alveolus for P1 (Fig. 2 B2); P2 is
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48 274 two rooted and has a high and mesially oriented single cusp (Fig. 2 B1 and E1–2).
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50 275 It is buccolingually rotated relative to the tooth row. The mesial and distal cristas
51
52 276 have sharp edges. It widens distally and has a marked distolingual cingulum. P3
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54 277 (Fig. 2 B2) is triangular in occlusal view, bicuspid and two rooted. Its cusps are
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3 278 distolingually oriented. The main cusp is very high and the distal accessory cusp is
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5 279 not very prominent. There is a marked lingual expansion, a broad lingual cingulum,
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7 280 and a concavity in the buccal wall. P4 of BAT-3'13.185 (Fig. 2 B2) is triangular,
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9 281 and robust. It has a very small and low parastyle located on its mesial cingulum
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11 282 (Fig. 2 B1). The protocone is subconical, robust, and located in line with the
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13 283 parastyle. There is a mesial soft inflection between the paracone and the parastyle.
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15 284 There is a poor developed concavity in the buccal wall. The paracone and metastyle
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17 285 form an elongate blade. The paracone is the highest and largest cusp, occupying
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19 286 over half of the total length of the tooth. It is triangular and distally inclined. The
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21 287 distal crista of the paracone has a slightly concave slope that fuses to the mesial
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23 288 crista of the metastyle via a U-shaped valley. The M1 (Fig. 2 B2) is rectangular,
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25 289 with the buccal wall narrower than the lingual one. The paracone is conical and
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27 290 situated on the mesiobuccal corner. It is the highest and most robust cusp, although
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29 291 the metacone is also quite well developed. There is a markedly swollen buccal
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31 292 cingulum. The styler area of the M1 is enlarged. The protocone is robust,
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33 293 subconical, and mesiolingually located. There is a very swollen lingual platform
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35 294 that does not completely enclose the protocone.
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40 **Mandible and Lower Dentition**—The mandible of the Batallones
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42 *Eomellivora* is long and robust (Fig. 3 A1–3, B 1–2, C). The BAT-3'08.526 (Fig. 3
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44 A1–3) and BAT-3'09.1000 (Fig. 3 C) have a total length of 120.79 mm 134.16 mm
45
46 297 respectively. The tooth row is straight and is aligned with the articular process. The
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48 298 mandibular corpus is deep, approximately twice the height of the m1, and is
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50 299 mediolaterally widened at the level of the paraconid of m1. The ventral margin is
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52 300 convex at the level of the ascending ramus and the mandibular symphysis, but it is
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54 301 concave from the p3 to the trigonid of m1. On the lateral side, there are two
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3 303 rounded mental foramina, one under p2 and the other beneath p3. The mandibular
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5 304 symphysis is rather vertical, being more evident in the larger hemimandibles (Fig. 3
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7 305 C). The muscle attachment of *M. digastricus* is on the caudoventral edge of the
8
9 306 mandibular corpus and reaches rostrally to beneath the m1 trigonid.

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11 The ascending ramus is rostrocaudally broad. Its dorsal border is sharp and
12
13 308 vertically oriented. The coronoid process is laterally rotated with an angle of ~75
14
15 309 degrees with respect to the articular process. The *M. temporalis pars profunda* and
16
17 310 the *M. temporalis pars superficialis* have their areas of insertion on the medial and
18
19 311 lateral sides of the ascending ramus respectively. The masseteric fossa is large,
20
21 312 oval, and relatively deep. Its rostral margin lies at the level of the m2. Inside the
22
23 313 masseteric fossa there is a noticeable and deep insertion area for the *M.*
24
25 314 *zygomaticomandibularis*. The *M. masseter pars superficialis* inserted on the
26
27 315 ventrolateral edge of the angular process, which also has a large insertion for the *M.*
28
29 316 *masseter pars profunda* near its ventrolateral margin. The articular process is large
30
31 317 and is widely separated from the angular process. The angular process is robust, is
32
33 318 caudally directed and on its medial side it has a well-developed muscular
34
35 319 attachment for *M. pterygoideus medialis*.

36
37 320 There are two deciduous teeth (dp3 and dp4) associated with BAT-10'12-G2-4
38
39 321 (Fig. 3 D1–8). The dp3 (Fig. 3 D3–5) is sigmoid-shaped, two rooted and
40
41 322 tricuspidate. The mesial accessory cuspid is very low; there is a small notch
42
43 323 between it and the main cusp. The main cuspid is high, lingually widened at the
44
45 324 base and somewhat mesially placed, with two sharp cristids. The distal accessory
46
47 325 cuspid is located on a cingulid. It is the lowest cuspid and has a large valley
48
49 326 between it and the main cuspid. The dp4 (Fig. 3 D6–8) is fragmentary. It is also two
50
51 327 rooted, elongated, and much larger than dp3. It preserves the buccal wall of the
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3 328 paraconid, a complete protoconid and a small fragment of the hypoconid with a tiny
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5 329 linguocclusal wall. The trigonid is similar to that of the m1, it has no metaconid and
6
7 330 possesses a convex buccal wall. The paraconid is low and reduced relative to the
8
9 331 protoconid. The protoconid is the highest cuspid. There is a wide valley between
10
11 332 the trigonid and the talonid. The adult lower dentition includes the c1, p2–4 and
12
13 333 m1–2. All the cuspids are aligned in the longitudinal axis. No lower incisors are
14
15 334 preserved. The lower canine in the BAT-3'08.526 (Fig. 3 A 1–3) is robust and
16
17 335 conical and has heavy occlusal wear. It has an oval cross-section, slightly broader at
18
19 336 the base and curved distally. Some longitudinal lines radiate from the apex to the
20
21 337 crown. The p1 is not preserved, but there is a single small alveolus in the larger
22
23 338 mandibles. The p2 (Fig. 3 A 1–3, C) is two rooted, with elliptical shape formed by
24
25 339 one cuspid mesially displaced. It is buccolingually rotated relative to the tooth row
26
27 340 and is elongated but with a slight distal widening. It has small mesiobuccal and
28
29 341 noticeable distobuccal cingulids. The p3 (Fig. 3 A 1–3) is bicuspidate. It has a
30
31 342 pronounced buccolingual widening. The main cuspid is elongated and
32
33 343 buccolingually compressed; its mesial and distal cristids have sharp edges. The
34
35 344 distal accessory cuspid is low and has a blunter morphology. The mesial buccal and
36
37 345 lingual cingulids are well developed. The p4 (Fig. 3 A 1–3, B1–3, C) has three
38
39 346 cuspids, and is sub-rectangular with a slight distal broadening. It is a relatively long
40
41 347 tooth compared to the total length of m1. It has a very small mesial accessory
42
43 348 cuspid. Its main cuspid is buccolingually compressed; the crown of p4 is higher
44
45 349 than that of the m1 paraconid. Its mesial and distal cristids have sharp edges. There
46
47 350 is a noticeable intercuspid notch between the main cuspid and the distal accessory
48
49 351 cuspid. The distal accessory cuspid is high, and blunt in BAT-3'09.1000, and low
50
51 352 in BAT-3'13.230, suggesting some degree of variability on this feature. Its main
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3 353 cuspid is inclined distally toward the m1 (see Appendix1). There is an occlusally
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5 354 projected mesial cingulid and a larger cingulid surrounding the distal accessory
6
7 355 cuspid. The m1 (Fig. 3 A1–3, B1–3, D1–2) is elongated and with a buccolingually
8
9 356 compressed talonid. The trigonid is a trenchant blade that occupies almost three
10
11 357 fourths of the total length of the tooth and has a prominent carnassial notch. The
12
13 358 protoconid is higher than the paraconid, and the two cuspids are located in the same
14
15 359 plane. There is no metaconid but there is a cristid that reaches the lingual area of
16
17 360 the talonid enclosing a vestigial basin. The talonid is high and located in line with
18
19 361 the trigonid cuspids; it is composed of a buccolingually-compressed hypoconid
20
21 362 occupying most of the talonid and a small centrally located hypoconulid only
22
23 363 perceptible in the not fully erupted and unworn m1 of BAT-10'12-G2-4 (Fig. 3
24
25 364 D1–2). There is no entoconid. The talonid has noticeable buccal and lingual
26
27 365 cingulids. The m2 (Fig. 3 D1–2) is uniradicate, tricuspidate and oval in occlusal
28
29 366 outline. As in the m1, the trigonid measures three fourths of the total length; its
30
31 367 cuspids are located in the same plane as the talonid cuspids of the m1. It has a low
32
33 368 and sharp paraconid, situated on a cingulid. The protoconid is the highest and
34
35 369 sharpest cuspid; it is located in a central position. There is a small notch between
36
37 370 the paraconid and the protoconid. The talonid has a central hypoconid on a well-
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39 371 developed cingulid.
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47 373 **Systematic Discussion**

48
49 374 The taxonomy of the genus *Eomellivora* has remained problematic because a
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51 375 substantial number of species have been named based on very scarce remains and
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53 376 the range of dental variation is largely unknown. For this reason we believe that the
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55 377 completeness of the sample of *Eomellivora* from Batallones (Figs. 4–9) presents a
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3 378 great opportunity to shed light on the systematics of the genus (Table 3).
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5 379 *Eomellivora piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965 was first described on the basis of a
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7 380 partial right hemimandible with i2-p4 and m1 trigonid, a fragment of maxilla with
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9 381 P4-M1, and an isolated M1 from Yassiören (Turkey), MN9 (Fig. 6 A1–3). Wolsan
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11 382 and Semenov (1996) included this taxon in *Eomellivora wimani* at the subspecific
12
13 383 rank of *E. wimani piveteaui*, and they chose the Yassiören hemimandible MNHN-
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15 384 TRQ-1004 as lectotype (Table 3). The similarities between the material from
16
17 385 Batallones and the Yassiören *Eomellivora* are striking (Valenciano et al, 2012),
18
19 386 especially BAT-3'09.1000 which has dentition of similar size and morphology
20
21 387 (Figs. 4–6) to the material described by Ozansoy (1965). However there are some
22
23 388 differences between the material such as the smaller relative size of the p2 and M1
24
25 389 and the more robust p3 in the Batallones-3 specimens (Fig. 8).
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29 390 The *Eomellivora* from Batallones includes five individuals (four from
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31 391 Batallones-3 and one from Batallones-10) and shows great size variation (Figs. 4–5,
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33 392 8, Table 1–2). This variability reaches up to 20% of the tooth length (e.g. m1), and
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35 393 appears to indicate the existence of marked sexual dimorphism in the genus, as
36
37 394 occurs in other extant and extinct mustelids (e.g. Zakrzewski, 1967; Moors, 1980;
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39 395 Hunt and Skolnick, 1996; Baskin, 1998; Ewer, 1998; Larivière and Jennings,
40
41 396 2009). Thus, we believe that sexual dimorphism can help us to interpret the
42
43 397 systematics of *Eomellivora*, and explain the larger size of some Batallones
44
45 398 specimens in relation to the material from Turkey. The two samples are similar in
46
47 399 the absence of a p2 distal accessory cuspid, and slight mesial accessory cuspid in
48
49 400 p3; similar robustness in p4 and P4; P4 shows a similar concavity in its buccal wall,
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51 401 with a robust protocone in line with the parastyle and the M1 has a conical
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53 402 paracone and a well-developed metacone, with a robust, subconical, and
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3 403 mesiolingually located protocone as well as patent buccal and lingual cingula.
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5 404 Therefore, the *Eomellivora* from Batallones-3 is conspecific with *E. piveteaui* from
6
7 405 Yassiören (Fig. 7). The specimen of *Eomellivora* from Batallones-10 cannot be
8
9 406 completely compared with the Yassiören sample because the only comparable
10
11 407 element, the m1 trigonid, is insufficient for comparative assessment. However this
12
13 408 specimen is metrically and morphologically similar to the Batallones-3 specimens,
14
15 409 and therefore we are confident in identifying it as *E. piveteaui*. An isolated m1
16
17 410 without roots belonging to a young adult described as Mellivorine gen. et sp. indet
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19 411 from Wissberg locality (Germany), MN9 (Tobien, 1955) was considered to belong
20
21 412 to *E. wimani piveteaui* by Morlo (1997). This m1 is similar in size to the largest
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23 413 teeth of the *E. piveteaui* sample from Batallones-3, the morphology of the m1
24
25 414 talonid is similar to the m1 from Batallones-10 and thus we assigned it to *E.*
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27 415 *piveteaui* (Fig. 7, Table 3).

31
32 416 Lungu (1978) ascribed a complete dental sample of one individual from Kalfa
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34 417 (Moldova) MN9, to *E. piveteaui*. With the exception of the single Wolsan and
35
36 418 Semenov (1996) manuscript, no other papers seem to have taken this description
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38 419 into account. This material completes the lectotype of *E. piveteaui* from Yassiören,
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40 420 except for the ascribed m2 (UST-CLF-N1-2027) that actually belongs to a hyaenid.
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42 421 The dentition from Kalfa is similar to that of *E. piveteaui* from Batallones, only
43
44 422 differing in the more developed M1 distal platform and a larger length of M1, p3 p4
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46 423 and more robust M1 and m1 in the *Eomellivora* from Moldavia (Figs. 4–8). Due to
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48 424 the larger size of the *E. piveteaui* from Kalfa and the older age of this locality in
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50 425 relation to *Eomellivora* from Batallones, these differences can be explained in
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52 426 terms of temporal differences or sexual dimorphism, and we agree with the
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54 427 taxonomic determination of Lungu (1978) (Table 3). Crusafont-Pairó and Ginsburg
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3 428 (1973) described very fragmentary material the taxon *Eomellivora liguritor*, from
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5 429 the Late Miocene (MN9) locality of Los Valles de Fuentidueña (Spain) consisting
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7 430 of an isolated M1 and a P4 without its protocone (Ginsburg et al., 1981). This
8
9 431 species was synonymized to *E. wimani piveteaui* by Wolsan and Semenov (1996).
10
11 432 The dentition is similar in size to *E. piveteaui* from Kalfa and *E. wimani* from
12
13 433 China, but based on the remains of Kalfa we think this Spanish material could be
14
15 434 assigned to *E. piveteaui* (Table 3). Koufos (2012) described and classified an
16
17 435 isolated and worn M1 from Ravin de la Pluie, Greece, MN10 as *E. wimani*.
18
19 436 However, it is metrically and morphologically similar to the M1 from Kalfa and
20
21 437 thus we reclassified it as belonging to *E. piveteaui* (Table 3).
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24
25 438 Of particular interest is the large sample of *Eomellivora* from the Ukrainian
26
27 439 site of Gritsev, MN9, identified by Wolsan and Semenov (1996) as *E. wimani*
28
29 440 *piveteaui* and more recently assigned to *E. wimani* (Morlo and Semenov, 2004;
30
31 441 Vangengeim et al., 2006) (Table 3). According to the biometric data provide by
32
33 442 Wolsan and Semenov (1996), the P2, M1, p2, and m1 are especially large, and in
34
35 443 some cases (P3, P4 and p2) relatively more slender than those of *E. piveteaui* from
36
37 444 Batallones (Figs. 4–5). However, without a full description it is difficult to say
38
39 445 more about the taxonomic assignment of this material, and the assignation of this
40
41 446 sample seems open to question until more information is available.
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44
45 447 Zdansky (1924) described the first fossil of *Eomellivora* under the name of *E.*
46
47 448 *wimani* based on one fragmentary skull and associated mandible from Shangyingou
48
49 449 or locality 12, Honan province, China, and another fragment of skull from
50
51 450 Liuwangou or Locality 31, Shansi province, China (Figs. 4–8, Table 3). Although
52
53 451 there are not geological surveys for Shangyingou in recent years, their assemblage
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55 452 is similar to the lower fossiliferous bed of Baode (T. Deng, pers. comm.). The
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3 453 updated biostratigraphy and paleomagnetic dating (Zhu et al., 2008; Kaakinen et
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5 454 al., 2013) of the sequence in the Baode area confine loc. 31 and very probably loc.
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7 455 12 as 7.2 Ma. This is roughly correlated in Europe to Late MN12-Lower MN13.
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9 456 *Eomellivora wimani* is the type species of the genus and the remains from
10
11 457 Shangyingou conform the lectotype (Fig. 6 B1–4).

14 458 Both individuals from China are very similar, but the lectotype is slightly
15
16 459 larger. On the other hand, the largest P3–P4 and p3–m1 from Batallones-3 are
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18 460 similar in size to the lectotype of *E. wimani*. (Figs. 4–5, 8). However the two
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20 461 species possess many morphological differences that clearly distinguish them (Fig.
21
22 462 6): *Eomellivora wimani* has a slightly shorter muzzle and more robust dentition,
23
24 463 specifically its P2 and p2. It also has a more pronounced concavity in the buccal
25
26 464 wall of its P2–P4, a strong mesial cingulum in P2, a mesial accessory cusp in its P3
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28 465 which a more developed mesial cingulum, together with a more reduced M1
29
30 466 metacone and a more robust M1 protocone than in *E. piveteaui*. *E. wimani* also
31
32 467 possess a centrally located M1 protocone, while the lingual platform completely
33
34 468 encloses the protocone, being mesiodistally larger than the *E. piveteaui* from
35
36 469 Batallones. The mesial accessory cusp is more developed in the p4; it has a more
37
38 470 robust m1 talonid with a more massive hypoconid, and the m2 of *E. wimani* seems
39
40 471 more derived than the m2 of *E. piveteaui*, with a single buccal cuspid in a central
41
42 472 position. Nevertheless, due to the fact that the Chinese specimen is worn, this last
43
44 473 interpretation might be questionable.

49 474 Other localities with *E. wimani* (Table 3) are Kern River Formation site 50
50
51 475 California, United States (Hemphillian, Hh2 according to Tedford et al., 2004 and
52
53 476 correlated to Late MN12-Lower MN13 according to Woodburne, 2010) described
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55 477 as *E. cf. wimani* by Stock and Hall (1933); Novaya Emetovka Ukraine, (MN12
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3 478 according to Semenov, 2001) described by Orlov (1948) as *E. aff. wimani*;
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5 479 Györszentmárton 2 Hungary (MN12 according to Nargolwalla et al., 2006)
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7 480 described by Kretzoi (1965) as *E. orlovi* and *E. rumana* from Cimisia, Moldova
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9 481 (MN12, according to Lungu and Rzebik-Kowalska, 2011) studied by Simionescu
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11 482 (1938).
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14 483 *Perunium ursogulo* from Grebeniki (Ukraine) was described by Orlov (1948),
15
16 484 based on a fragment of skull and two mandibles (Fig. 6 C1–3). The age of this
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18 485 locality is MN11 (Wolsan and Semenov, 1996), although recently studies suggest
19
20 486 an older age (MN10, Vangengeim and Tesakov, 2013). Due to the strong similarity
21
22 487 with *Eomellivora*, Ozansoy (1965) subsumed *Perunium* in this genus and Wolsan
23
24 488 and Semenov (1996) synonymized it with *E. wimani wimani*. The dental
25
26 489 morphology of the Ukrainian sample is intermediate between *E. piveteaui* and *E.*
27
28 490 *wimani*, but it possesses significant differences from both species (Fig. 6): On the
29
30 491 one hand it shares a buccal concavity poorly developed in P4, a M1 metacone more
31
32 492 developed, and a mesolingually positioned M1 protocone with *E. piveteaui*. On the
33
34 493 other hand, it differs from *E. piveteaui* in its relatively shorter muzzle; more robust
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36 494 dentition (especially the p3 with a very strong distal widening); a mesiodistally
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38 495 reduced P4 protocone; more accessory cuspids in p2–p4; larger and more derived
39
40 496 m2 with a reduced single cuspid placed in a central position together with a
41
42 497 mesiodistal cristid. Moreover, *E. ursogulo* shares with *E. wimani* a robust P2, P3,
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44 498 p2, p3; strongly developed lingual cingulum in P2 and mesial cingulum in P3; more
45
46 499 highly developed premolar accessory cuspid, and the lingual platform of M1
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48 500 completely encloses the protocone. Although *E. ursogulo* seems to possess a
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50 501 mixture of morphological features of *E. piveteaui* and *E. wimani*, it also appears to
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52 502 be a highly derived species, having some notable autoapomorphies that, in our
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3 503 opinion, supports the taxon as a separate species (Table 3). The autoapomorphies
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5 504 include: small additional cusp in the P4 parastyle, P3 with two distal accessory
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7 505 cusps, lingual platform of M1 with an inflexion, and highly developed p3 mesial
8
9 506 accessory cuspid. *Eomellivora ursogulo* has also been diagnosed outside Ukraine
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11 507 from Borský Svätý Jur (Slovakia) MN11 (Lupták, 1995). However, a more recent
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13 508 paper by Kováč et al. (2006) revised the age of this site to MN9 and identified the
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15 509 material as *E. wimani*. Due to the scarcity of the material, we prefer to classify the
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17 510 Slovakian specimens as *Eomellivora sp.* (Fig. 7, Table 3).

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21 511 *Eomellivora hungarica*, Kretzoi, 1942 from Polgardi 2 (Hungary) and
22
23 512 synonymized as *E. wimani wimani* (Wolsan and Semenov, 1996), was described on
24
25 513 the basis of a mandible fragment with c1 and p4–m1 and isolated M1 (Fig. 6 D1–2,
26
27 514 Table 3); the age of the locality is MN13 (Hír and Kökay, 2010). *Eomellivora*
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29 515 *hungarica* differs from *E. piveteaui* in its shorter mandible and reduced number of
30
31 516 lower premolars, its larger size and more robust dentition. The most remarkable
32
33 517 feature of this species is the great robustness and length of its p4 (Figs. 4–8). This
34
35 518 tooth shows a well-marked backward inclination of the cuspids with a clear
36
37 519 imbrication with the mesial part of the m1. Also the m1 has a strong central
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39 520 hypoconid with very marked lingual cristid. However, its M1 looks very similar to
40
41 521 that of *E. piveteaui*, suggesting a robust form with some degree of affinity with *E.*
42
43 522 *piveteaui*. Kretzoi (1942) also described *E. hungarica altera* from Csákvar locality
44
45 523 (Hungary), MN 11 (Hír and Kökay, 2010) based on three isolated teeth (P3, P4 and
46
47 524 m1). Wolsan and Semenov (1996) synonymized it with *E. wimani wimani*. Despite
48
49 525 substantial differences such as large upper dentition and a P3 with large lingual
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51 526 projection, there is not enough material to compare it with the other species of
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53 527 *Eomellivora*. We believe this material likely represents a distinct taxon and yet
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3 528 because of the scarcity of the material and its lack of definitive diagnostic features
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5 529 we assign them for now simply to *Eomellivora* sp. (Figs. 4–5, 8, Table 3).
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7 530 In the review of the Eurasian and North American *Eomellivora* material
8
9 531 Wolsan and Semenov (1996) considered this material to represent a single lineage
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11 532 of *Eomellivora*, subdivided into two chronosubspecies: one Vallesian (MN9–10) *E.*
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13 533 *wimani piveteaui* (including the material previously assigned to *E. liguritor*
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15 534 Crusafont-Pairó and Ginsburg, 1973, from Los Valles de Fuentidueña) and another
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17 535 Turolian/Ventian (MN11–13) *E. wimani wimani*, including the specimens of *E.*
18
19 536 *ursogulo* (Orlov, 1948) from Grebeniki, *E. hungarica* Kretzoi, 1942, from Polgardi
20
21 537 2, *E. orlovi* Kretzoi, 1965, from Györszentmárton 2 and *E. rumana* Simionescu,
22
23 538 1938, from Cimislia. Although the taxonomic proposal put forth by Wolsan and
24
25 539 Semenov (1996) has been accepted by several authors (e.g. Morlo, 1997; Qiu,
26
27 540 2003; Werdelin, 2003; Koufos 2012), in view of the distinct morphological
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29 541 differences between the samples it seems more reasonable to consider the existence
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31 542 of at least four species (*E. piveteaui*, *E. wimani*, *E. ursogulo* and *E. hungarica*) as
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33 543 discussed above (Figs. 4–8, Table 3).
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38 544 More recently Morales and Pickford (2005) described the African *E.*
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40 545 *tugenensis*, from Ngorora Fm (Kenya), dated to about 12 Ma. This species is based
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42 546 on a fragmentary skull that contains a P4 with broken protocone and a complete
43
44 547 M1. It is a primitive *Eomellivora* morphologically similar to *E. wimani* but much
45
46 548 smaller (Werdelin and Peigne, 2010), being approximately intermediate in size
47
48 549 between the extant *G. gulo* and *M. capensis*. The proportions of the P4 of *E.*
49
50 550 *tugenensis* are similar to *G. gulo*, and thus very different than the other species of
51
52 551 *Eomellivora*, but the proportions of the M1 are similar to the species of this genus
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54 552 (Figs. 4–5, 7–8), suggesting that these African remains could correspond to an
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3 553 ancestral form of the genus, though more material is needed to address this
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5 554 hypothesis.

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10 556 **Phylogenetic Analysis**

11 557 To better assess the relationships of *E. piveteaui* to other species of
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13 558 *Eomellivora* and within Mustelidae, we performed a cladistic analysis of 9 taxa and
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16 559 43 dental characters being equally weighted and unordered (Figs. 7, 9). The
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18 560 complete list of taxa, characters and character-taxon matrix are available in
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20 561 Appendix 1–2. We restricted our analysis of the fossils to *E. piveteaui* from
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22 562 Batallones, *E. wimani* from Shangyingou and *E. ursogulo* from Grebeniki – the
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24
25 563 only specimens with complete dental remains. Cladistic analysis was performed on
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27 564 this data set using in PAUP*4.0b10 (Swofford, 2002). A bootstrap analysis was
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29 565 performed using 1000 replicates to test for resulting clade support. This analysis
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31 566 yielded a bootstrap tree of 98 steps, with a consistency index (CI) = 0.4592, a
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33 567 homoplasy index (HI) = 0.5408 and a retention index (RI) = 0.3977.

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36 568 The cladogram shows *Eomellivora* is the sister taxon of the extant *Mellivora*
37
38 569 *capensis* (bootstrap 65%), and thus it is consistent to include it in the subfamily
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40 570 Mellivorinae (Fig. 9). This subfamily is characterized by a robust P3, with a high
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42 571 crown and marked buccal concavity, long relative to the P4; robust P4 with longer
43
44 572 protocone; p4 relatively long and inclined backward; m1 without metaconid, with a
45
46 573 narrow talonid composed by a central hypoconid. Additionally, the monophyletic
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48 574 group of *Eomellivora* is a well-supported clade (71% bootstrap support) (Fig. 9)
49
50 575 characterized by M1 relatively slender with enlarged styler area, and a very swollen
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52 576 lingual cingulum; m1 trigonid occupying almost three fourths of the total length of
53
54 577 the tooth with a high talonid composed of a buccolingually-compressed hypoconid;
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3 578 m2 without metaconid. *E. wimani* and *E. ursogulo* form a well-supported crown
4
5 579 group (91% bootstrap support) (Fig. 9) characterized by a triangular P2 with a
6
7 580 strong lingual cingulum and a buccal concavity on the wall; P3 with mesial
8
9 581 accessory cuspid present and very marked mesial cingulum; lingual platform of M1
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11 582 enclosed completely the protocone; p2 very robust; p3 with a buccolingual
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13 583 platform; p4 with a high mesial accessory cuspid.

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16 584 Our phylogenetic hypothesis (Figs. 7, 9) indicates that *E. piveteaui* (MN9–10)
17
18 585 had a common ancestor with the crown group *E. wimani*–*E. ursogulo* (MN11–13).
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20 586 *Eomellivora piveteaui* is found in Eurasia during the biozone MN9 and MN10,
21
22 587 being present in Western Europe (Los Valles de Fuentidueña and Batallones,
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24 588 Spain), Central Europe (Wissberg, Germany), Oriental Europe (Kalfa, Ukraine),
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26 589 Greece (Rabin de la Plui) and Turkey (Yassiören). During the Turolian MN11–12
27
28 590 appear two more robust species of *Eomellivora*: *E. ursogulo* from Grebeniki, only
29
30 591 found in Ukraine and the most common *E. wimani* found in Oriental Europe
31
32 592 (Novaya Emetovka 2, Ukraine and Cmislia, Moldova), China (Shangyingou and
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34 593 Liuwangou), and North America (Kern river Formation). Finally, the genus reaches
35
36 594 the end of the Miocene, Ventian, MN13 (Morales et al., 2013) with a large and
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38 595 robust species (*E. hungarica*) which has only been recorded in Polgardi 2
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40 596 (Hungary).

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46 47 598 INSIGHTS INTO THE DIET OF *EOMELLIVORA*

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51 600 The dentition of *E. piveteaui* has a mixture of features that can help us to
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53 601 interpret the feeding habits of this species. On the one hand, *E. piveteaui* possesses
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55 602 traits that can be interpreted as hypercarnivorous, based on features that may
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3 603 emphasize a shearing function: (1) straight dental series; (2) long and
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5 604 buccolingually compressed m1 trigonid; (3) loss of the m1 metaconid. All of these
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7 605 are features it shares with the extant *Gulo gulo* and *Mellivora capensis* and as well
8
9 606 as with the extinct *Ekorus ekakeran*, *Megalictis ferox*, and the other species of
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11 607 *Eomellivora*; (4) the presence of a trenchant hypoconid centrally located on m1
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13 608 talonid, shared with all species of *Eomellivora* which shows a higher and more
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15 609 buccolingually compressed hypoconid than *M. ferox* and *Ekorus ekakeran*, and (5)
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17 610 m1 and m2 cuspids in line with the dental series, thereby increasing the length of
18
19 611 cutting edges. In contrast, *Eomellivora piveteaui* possesses other characteristics that
20
21 612 could be interpreted as adaptations to durophagy and/or carcass processing: (1) p3–
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23 613 p4 blunt posterior accessory cuspids; (2) P4 protocone robust; (3) robust M1 lingual
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25 614 cingulum; and (4) distal widening of P3 and p3. Lungu (1978) suggests *E. piveteaui*
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27 615 as a smaller size *Eomellivora* with a more slender dentition than *E. wimani*, *E.*
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29 616 *ursogulo*, *E. hungarica* and *Eomellivora* from Csakvar, being a more primitive and
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31 617 less specialized species for crushing bones. Consequently, the complete sample of
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33 618 *E. piveteaui* from Batallones has allowed us to distinguish the existence of two
34
35 619 dietary ecomorphotypes in the genus: (1) a smaller size group of *Eomellivora*
36
37 620 adapted to a more hypercarnivorous diet composed of *E. piveteaui* (Fig. 8), similar
38
39 621 to that of the hypercarnivorous *Ekorus ekakeran*; (2) and a larger and robust
40
41 622 *Eomellivora* composed of *E. wimani*, *E. ursogulo*, *E. hungarica*, and *Eomellivora*
42
43 623 *sp.* from Csakvar characterized by having greater dimensions, and a higher and a
44
45 624 greater number of blunt accessory cusps (Fig. 8), that may be adapted to a diet with
46
47 625 a higher proportion of bone, similar to the extant durophage *G. gulo* (Larivière and
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49 626 Jennings, 2009) (though the higher number of accessory cusps would indicate
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51 627 greater hypercarnivory by some metrics; Hartstone-Rose 2011, Hartstone-Rose and
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3 628 Stynder 2013). The widening of some premolars, together with the more sectorial
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5 629 dentition in *E. piveteaui* could be considered a hypercarnivorous specialization
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7 630 towards a more hypercarnivorous canid-like animal, capable of processing bones
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9 631 with its molars to maximize access to the available food.

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11 632 *Eomellivora piveteaui* (Fig. 10) could have accessed a wide variety of prey
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13 633 items present in the fauna of Batallones. It likely occupied an ecological niche of an
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15 634 active predator of medium to large prey such as moschids, small to medium size
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17 635 bovids, young suids or cervids, while maintaining the ability to hunt small prey
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19 636 such as reptiles, birds and lagomorphs. It may have occupied an intermediate
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21 637 ecological role between the opportunistic extant *Mellivora capensis* and the
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23 638 predominantly scavenging extant *G. gulo*. Moreover, *E. piveteaui* may have used its
24
25 639 dentition to more fully process carcasses of its own prey, as happens with *M.*
26
27 640 *capensis* which is capable of consuming prey entirely, including small bones (e.g.,
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29 641 large lizards, snakes or small mammals), but not so much as the efficient scavenger
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31 642 *G. gulo* (Ewer, 1998; Begg et al., 2003; Larivière and Jennings, 2009). Moreover,
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33 643 the preliminary observations about the postcranial remains of *E. piveteaui* from
34
35 644 Batallones show that the taxon had relatively long fore- and hindlimbs similar to
36
37 645 extant canids who tend to have a high proportion of meat in their diet (e.g., *Canis*
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39 646 *lupus*). This could suggest possible cursorial adaptations in *E. piveteaui*. Future
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41 647 study of the postcranial remains could help determine whether this taxon was a
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43 648 pursuit predator and shed light on our understanding of its role in the Batallones
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45 649 ecosystem.

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51 651 CONCLUSIONS

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3 653 The craniomandibular features of the material from Batallones is assigned to
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5 654 the *Eomellivora piveteaui*, Ozansoy, 1965, providing a fuller picture of this species,
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7 655 supplementing the previously known material from Yassiören and allowing the
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9 656 increased validation of the taxon at the specific level. The sample of *E. piveteaui*
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11 657 from Batallones permits the refinement of the diagnosis of the species, as well as
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13 658 expanding its age to MN10. Moreover, detailed comparisons with the rest of the
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15 659 species of *Eomellivora* show several morphological features that lead us to accept,
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17 660 *E. piveteaui*, *E. wimani*, *E. ursogulo* and *E. hungarica*. *Eomellivora* is the sister
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19 661 taxon of the extant *Mellivora capensis* and *E. piveteaui* had a common ancestor
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21 662 with the crown group *E. wimani*-*E. ursogulo*. *Eomellivora piveteaui* was a large
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23 663 mustelid (Fig. 10) adapted to a more hypercarnivorous diet than the largest extant
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25 664 terrestrial mustelids (e.g., *G. gulo* and *M. capensis*) and the other species of
26
27 665 *Eomellivora* and also shows some bone-crushing or carcass processing adaptations.
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29 666 In addition, we suggest that *E. piveteaui* may have had an active predatory role
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31 667 exploiting both small and relatively large prey.
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54
55 677 Kalfa), L. Werdelin, Swedish Museum of Natural History, Stockholm, Sweden (*E.*
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3 678 *wimani* from Shangyingou), P. Joniack, Comenius University, Bratislava, Slovakia
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FIGURE CAPTIONS

- 988
989 FIGURE 1. **A**, Simplified geographic map of the Iberian Peninsula with the
990 Tertiary basins shaded and the Madrid Province outlined; **B**, detailed map of the
991 Madrid Province with the situation of Cerro de los Batallones fossil complex; **C**,
992 aerial photo showing the position of the areas of systematic excavations (indicated
993 as empty circles) with the sites with presence of *Eomellivora piveteaui*, Batallones-
994 3 and 10 (BAT-3 and BAT-10 respectively), designated with a star. [planned for
995 column width]
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997 FIGURE 2. Skull and upper dentition of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from Batallones

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3 998 localities. Please see supplementary material online (Supplementary Data 1, Figure
4
5 999 1S) for a digital rendering of BAT-3'09.1000 that can be manipulated in 3D space.
6
7 1000 **A1**, dorsal view of skull BAT-3'09.1000; **A2**, rostral view of skull BAT-3'09.1000;
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9 1001 **A3**, lateral view of skull BAT-3'09.1000; **A4**, caudal view of skull BAT-3'09.1000;
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11 1002 **B1**, lateral view of skull BAT-3'13.185; **B2**, ventral view of skull BAT-3'13.185;
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13 1003 **C1**, medial view of I3 BAT-3'09.688; **C2**, distal view of I3 BAT-3'09.688; **D**,
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15 1004 lingual view of C1 BAT-3'08.635; **E1**, lingual view of P2 BAT-10'08-G4-102; **E2**,
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17 1005 buccal view of P2 BAT-10'08-G4-102; **E3**, occlusal view of P2 BAT-10'08-G4-
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19 1006 102; Scale bar for A1–4 and B1–2 equals 5 cm and scale bar for C1–2, D and E1–3
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21 1007 equals 2 cm [planned for page width]
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27 1009 FIGURE 3. Mandibles and lower dentition of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from
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29 1010 Batallones. **A1**, lateral view of mandible BAT-3'08.526. Please see supplementary
30
31 1011 material online (Supplementary Data 1, Figure 2S) for a digital rendering of BAT-
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33 1012 3'08.526 that can be manipulated in 3D space; **A2**, medial view of mandible BAT-
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35 1013 3'08.526; **A3**, occlusal view of mandible BAT-3'08.526; **B1**, lateral view of
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37 1014 mandible BAT-3'13.230; **B2**, medial view of mandible BAT-3'13.230; **B3**,
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39 1015 occlusal view of mandible BAT-3'13.230; **C**, lateral view of the right mandible
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41 1016 associated to skull BAT-3'09.1000; **D1**, occlusal view of m1 and m2 associated to
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43 1017 juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; **D2**, lingual view of m1 and m2 associated to
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45 1018 juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; **D3**, buccal view of dp3 associated to juvenile
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47 1019 mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; **D4**, lingual view of dp3 associated to juvenile
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49 1020 mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; **D5**, occlusal view of dp3 associated to juvenile
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51 1021 mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; **D6**, buccal view of dp4 associated to juvenile
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53 1022 mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4 **D7**, lingual view of dp4 associated to juvenile mandible
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3 1023 BAT-10'12-G2-4; **D8**, occlusal view of dp4 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-
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5 1024 10'12-G2-4. Scale bar for A1–3, B1–3 and C equals 5 cm and scale bar for D1–8
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7 1025 equals 2 cm [planned for page width]
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11 1027 FIGURE 4. Relationships between lengths (L) and widths (W) of upper dentition in
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13 1028 *Eomellivora*. Sources: **SH** (Shangyingou), Zdansky (1924); **LI** (Liuwangou),
14
15 1029 Zdansky (1924); **GRT** (Gritsev), Wolsan and Semenov (1996); **NO** (Novaya
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17 1030 Emetovka), Orlov (1948); **GYÖ** (Györszentmárton), Kretzoi (1965), **KRF** (Kern
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19 1031 River Formation site 50), Stock and Hall (1933); **CIM** (Cimislia), Wolsan and
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21 1032 Semenov (1996); **YAS** (Yassiören), Ozansoy (1965) and for P4 and M1,
22
23 1033 estimations based on pictures of MNHN-TRQ-1005, instead of the evidently
24
25 1034 confused original data provided on Ozansoy (1965); **WSS** (Wissberg), Tobien
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27 1035 (1955); **RPI** (Ravin de la Pluie), Koufos (2012); **BAT** (Batallones), this paper;
28
29 1036 **LVF** (Los Valles de Fuentidueña), Crusafont-Pairó and Ginsburg (1973) and for p2
30
31 1037 this paper; **KLF** (Kalfa), Lungu (1978) and for M1 this paper, estimations based on
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33 1038 text-fig.9 in Lungu (1978), instead of the apparently mistaken original data given in
34
35 1039 table 2; **GRE** (Grbeniki), Orlov (1948); **NG** (2/11 locality, Ngorora Formation),
36
37 1040 Morales and Pickford (2005); **BOJ** (Borský Svätý Jur), Lupták (1995); **CSA**
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39 1041 (Csárkvar), Kretzoi (1942); **POL** (Polgardi 2) [planned for 2/3 of a whole page
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41 1042 width]
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45 1044 FIGURE 5. Relationships between lengths (L) and widths (W) of lower dentition in
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47 1045 *Eomellivora*. Legend and Source, the same of figure 4. [planned for 2/3 of a whole
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3 1048 FIGURE 6. Main comparative material of species of *Eomellivora* recognized in this
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5 1049 paper. **A1**, MNHN-TRQ-1005, *Eomellivora piveteaui* from Yassiören (YAS),
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7 1050 occlusal view of maxilla fragment with P4 and M1; **A2**, MNHN-TRQ-1004,
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9 1051 lectotype of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from YAS, lateral view of mandible fragment;
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11 1052 **A3**, MNHN-TRQ-1004 occlusal view; **B1**, PMU-M3692, holotype of *Eomellivora*
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13 1053 *wimani* from Shangyingou (SH), lateral view of skull fragment with complete
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15 1054 upper dentition; **B2**, PMU-M3692, ventral view; **B3**, PMU-M3693, holotype of
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17 1055 *Eomellivora wimani* from SH, lateral view of mandible fragment with complete
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19 1056 lower dentition; **B4**, PMU-M3693, occlusal view; **C1**, PIN-No. 268 holotype of
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21 1057 *Eomellivora ursogulo* from Grebeniki (GRE), occlusal view; **C2**, PIN-No. 269a,
22
23 1058 holotype of *Eomellivora ursogulo* from GRE, lateral view of mandible with
24
25 1059 complete lower dentition; **C3**, PIN-No. 269a, occlusal view; **D1**, MFGI-Ob-2676,
26
27 1060 holotype of *Eomellivora hungarica* from Polgardi 2 (POL), lateral view of
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29 1061 mandible with fragmentary p3, p4 and m1; **D2**, MFGI-Ob-2676, occlusal view.
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34 1062 .Scale bar equals 5 cm. [planned for page width]
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38 1064 FIGURE 7. **A**, Chronostratigraphic position of the fossil localities where
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40 1065 *Eomellivora* are found, according to, Tobien, (1955); Ginsburg et al., (1981);
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42 1066 Wolsan and Semenov, (1996); Lunkka et al., (1999); Semenov, (2001); Morlo and
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44 1067 Semenov, (2004); Tedford et al., (2004); Morales and Pickford (2005), Nargolwalla
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46 1068 et al., (2006); Kováč et al. (2006); Morales et al., (2008); Zhu et al., (2008); Hír and
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48 1069 Kökay, (2010); Woodburne, (2010); Lungu and Rzebik-Kowalska, (2011); Koufos,
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50 1070 (2012); Kaakinen et al., (2013); Vangengeim and Tesakov, (2013); **B**, Calibrated
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52 1071 hypothesis phylogenetic based on Appendix 1–2 (see figure 9 for more details).
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5 1074 FIGURE 8. Ratio diagram of all *Eomellivora* described in the bibliography. The

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7 1075 dental measurements of *Gulo gulo* B.1280 serve as the standard for comparison

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9 1076 (solid line at Y axis equal to 100) Legend and Source, the same of figure 4.

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11 1077 [planned for 2/3 of a whole page width]

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16 1079 FIGURE 9. Phylogenetic relationships of *Eomellivora piveteaui* within Musteloidea

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18 1080 (Carnivora). A Bootstrap tree (98 steps; CI = 0.4592; HI= 0.5408; RI=0.3977) has

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20 1081 been obtained by means of PAUP*4.0b10 (Swofford, 2002). The outgroup was

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22 1082 *Canis lupus* (Linnaeus, 1758). Character/taxa matrix is detailed in the Appendix 1–

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24 1083 2. Apomorphic characters supporting each node: Node A: 2 (1); 8 (1); 9 (1); 10 (1);

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26 1084 13 (1); 15 (1); 31 (1); 37 (1); 38 (1); 40 (1); 42 (1); Node B: 7(1); 20 (1); 21 (1); 22

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28 1085 (1); 39 (1); 41 (1), 43 (1); Node C: 4 (1); 5 (1); 6 (1); 11 (1); 14 (1); 25 (1); 28 (2);

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30 1086 30 (1); 33 (1).

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36 1088 FIGURE 10. Sequential reconstruction of the head of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from

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38 1089 Batallones in lateral view. **A**, life appearance; **B**, reconstructed skull and mandible;

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40 1090 Skull and mandible BAT-3'09.1000. Artwork by Adam Hartstone-Rose. [planned

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43 1091 for page width]

APPENDIX 1. Description of characters used in phylogenetic analyses.

- (1) P1. Present (0); absent (1).
- (2) P2. The largest axis of P2 in line with P3 (0); the largest axis of P2 rotated (1).
- (3) P2. Distal accessory cusp of P2 absent (0); present (1).
- (4) P2. Occlusal morphology: subrectangular (0); triangular (1); oval (2).
- (5) P2. Marked concavity in the buccal wall: absent (0); present (1).
- (6) P2. Lingual cingulum weak (0); strong (1).
- (7) P3. Occlusal morphology: subrectangular with an absent or reduced lingual expansion (0); triangular with a well-developed lingual expansion.
- (8) P3. Robustness ratio [(maximum width/ maximum length) x 100]: slender P3 (less than 50) (0), robust P3 (more than 50) (1).
- (9) P3. Maximum length of P3 in relation to maximum length of P4 ratio [(L P3/L P4) x 100]: P3 relatively reduced (less than 55) (0); P3 relatively long (more than 55).
- (10) P3. Ratio between the height of P3 and P4 paracone [(Maximum height P3/ Maximum height P4) x 100]: height P3 not enlarged (less than 65) (0); height P3 enlarged (more than 65).
- (11) P3. Development of the mesial accessory cuspid reduced or absent (0); present (1).
- (12) P3. At least one distal accessory cuspid present (0); absent (1).
- (13) P3. Marked concavity in the buccal wall: absent (0); present (1).
- (14) P3. Mesial cingulum poorly developed (0); strong or very developed (1).
- (15) P4. Robustness ratio [(maximum width/ maximum length) x 100] and size of the protocone: slender P4 with (less than 60) slender protocone (0); robust P4 (more than 60) with robust protocone.
- (16) P4. Protocone in line with the mesiobuccal corner or surpass the mesiobuccal corner of the tooth (0); protocone distal to the mesiobuccal corner.
- (17) P4. Without parastyle or poor-developed parastyle (0); strong parastyle(1).
- (18) P4. Mesial inflection between the paracone and the parastyle: deep (0); shallow (1).
- (19) P4. Pronounced concavity in the buccal wall: absent (0); present (1).
- (20) M1. Robustness ratio [(maximum width on the buccolingual area/ maximum length) x 100]: slender M1 (from 130 to 150); very slender M1 (more than 160).
- (21) M1. Cingulum of M1 conspicuously swollen buccally: absent (0); present (1).
- (22) M1. Development of the stylar area small (0); enlarged or very developed (1).
- (23) M1. Metacone not reduced (0); reduced (1).

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3 (24) M1. Protocone mesolingually located (0); almost centrally on the middle of the
4 talonid.
5
6 (25) M1. Lingual platform not completely enclose the protocone (0); completely
7 enclose the protocone (1).
8
9 (26) p1. Present (0); absent (1).
10
11 (27) p2. Development of the distal accessory cuspid present (0); reduced or absent (1).
12
13 (28) p2. Robustness ratio [(maximum width/ maximum length) x 100]: slender p2 (less
14 than 50); relatively robust p2 (from 50 to 70); very robust p2 (more than 70).
15
16 (29) p3. Development of the distal accessory cuspid present and well developed (0);
17 absent or poorly-developed (1).
18
19 (30) p3. Buccolingual platform of the crown absent (0); present (1).
20
21 (31) p4. Length ratio in relation to m1 [(maximum length p4/ maximum length m1) x
22 100]: p4 not reduced (from 50 to 60) (0); p4 relatively enlarged (more than 60) (1).
23
24 (32) p4. Ratio between the height of p4 and m1 paraconid [(Maximum height p4/
25 Maximum height m1 paraconid) x 100]: p4 lower than m1 paraconid (less than 100) (0);
26 p4 higher than m1 paraconid (more than 100).
27
28 (33) p4. Development of the messial acesyory cuspid absent or poorly-developed (0);
29 present with great high development.
30
31 (34) p4. Development of the distal accessory cuspid present and well-developed (0);
32 absent or vestigial(1).
33
34 (35) p4. Development of a metaconid or labial accessory cuspid absent (0); incipient or
35 developed (1).
36
37 (36) p4. Development of a conspicuous buccodistal ledge absent (0); present (1).
38
39 (37) p4. Backward inclination of the main cuspid: p4 practically vertical (90°–80°) (0);
40 p4 with backward inclination (less than 80°).
41
42 (38) m1. Development of the metaconid present (0); absent (1).
43
44 (39) m1. Relative length of talonid with respect the total m1 length: the talonid 1/3 of
45 the total length (0); equal or less than 1/4 of the total length (1).
46
47 (40) m1. Maximum buccolingual width of m1 located in talonid (0); narrow talonid
48 without the maximum buccolingual width in the talonid.
49
50 (41) m1. Height of hypoconid [(height of m1 hypoconid / height m1 protoconid) x 100]:
51 short hypoconid (equal or lees than 50) (0); tall hypoconid (equal or more than 60).
52
53 (42) m1. Size and position of hypoconid: small size and labially located (0); strong and
54 central position (1).
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56 (43) m2. Development of the metaconid present (0); absent (1).
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APPENDIX 2. Character-taxon matrix used for phylogenetic analysis.

Taxon	1 0	2 0	3 0	4 0
<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i>	0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1	0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1	1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0	1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1
<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>	0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ?	1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1	1 1 1 1 1 0 1 2 0 1	1 ? 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1
<i>Eomellivora ursogulo</i>	0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ?	1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1	1 1 0 0 1 0 0 2 0 1	1 ? 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1
<i>Gulo gulo</i>	0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0	0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1	1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0	0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1
<i>Mellivora capensis</i>	1 1 1 2 0 1 0 1 1 1	0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0	0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0	1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1
<i>Pekania pennanti</i>	0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0	0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0	1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0	0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0
<i>Eira barbara</i>	1 0 1 2 0 0 0 1 1 1	0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1	0 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0	1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0
<i>Martes martes</i>	0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1	0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0	1 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0	0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0
<i>Canis lupus</i>	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0	1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0

FIGURE 1. A, Simplified geographic map of the Iberian Peninsula with the Tertiary basins shaded and the Madrid Province outlined; B, detailed map of the Madrid Province with the situation of Cerro de los Batallones fossil complex; C, aerial photo showing the position of the areas of systematic excavations (indicated as empty circles) with the sites with presence of *Eomellivora piveteaui*, Batallones-3 and 10 (BAT-3 and BAT-10 respectively), designated with a star. [planned for column width]
191x460mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 2. Skull and upper dentition of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from Batallones localities. Please see supplementary material online (Supplementary Data 1, Figure 1S) for a digital rendering of BAT-3'09.1000 that can be manipulated in 3D space. A1, dorsal view of skull BAT-3'09.1000; A2, rostral view of skull BAT-3'09.1000; A3, lateral view of skull BAT-3'09.1000; A4, caudal view of skull BAT-3'09.1000; B1, lateral view of skull BAT-3'13.185; B2, ventral view of skull BAT-3'13.185; C1, medial view of I3 BAT-3'09.688; C2, distal view of I3 BAT-3'09.688; D, lingual view of P2 BAT-10'08-G4-102; E1, lingual view of P2 BAT-10'08-G4-102; E2, buccal view of P2 BAT-10'08-G4-102; E3, occlusal view of P2 BAT-10'08-G4-102; Scale bar for A1-4 and B1-2 equals 5 cm and scale bar for C1-2, D and E1-3 equals 2 cm [planned for page width] 233x296mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 3. Mandibles and lower dentition of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from Batallones. A1, lateral view of mandible BAT-3'08.526. Please see supplementary material online (Supplementary Data 1, Figure 2S) for a digital rendering of BAT-3'08.526 that can be manipulated in 3D space; A2, medial view of mandible BAT-3'08.526; A3, occlusal view of mandible BAT-3'08.526; B1, lateral view of mandible BAT-3'13.230; B2, medial view of mandible BAT-3'13.230; B3, occlusal view of mandible BAT-3'13.230; C, lateral view of the right mandible associated to skull BAT-3'09.1000; D1, occlusal view of m1 and m2 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; D2, lingual view of m1 and m2 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; D3, buccal view of dp3 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; D4, lingual view of dp3 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; D5, occlusal view of dp3 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; D6, buccal view of dp4 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; D7, lingual view of dp4 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4; D8, occlusal view of dp4 associated to juvenile mandible BAT-10'12-G2-4. Scale bar for A1-3, B1-3 and C equals 5 cm and scale bar for D1-8 equals 2 cm [planned for page width] 209x241mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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FIGURE 4. Relationships between lengths (L) and widths (W) of upper dentition in *Eomellivora*. Sources: SH (Shangyingou), Zdansky (1924); LI (Liuwangou), Zdansky (1924); GRT (Gritsev), Wolsan and Semenov (1996); NO (Novaya Emetovka), Orlov (1948); GYÖ (Györszentmárton), Kretzoi (1965), KRF (Kern River Formation site 50), Stock and Hall (1933); CIM (Cimislia), Wolsan and Semenov (1996); YAS (Yassiören), Ozansoy (1965) and for P4 and M1, estimations based on pictures of MNHN-TRQ-1005, instead of the evidently confused original data provided on Ozansoy (1965); WSS (Wissberg), Tobien (1955); RPI (Ravin de la Pluie), Koufos (2012); BAT (Batallones), this paper; LVF (Los Valles de Fuentidueña), Crusafont-Pairó and Ginsburg (1973) and for p2 this paper; KLF (Kalfa), Lungu (1978) and for M1 this paper, estimations based on text-fig.9 in Lungu (1978), instead of the apparently mistaken original data given in table 2; GRE (Grbeniki), Orlov (1948); NG (2/11 locality, Ngorora Formation), Morales and Pickford (2005); BOJ (Borský Svätý Jur), Lupták (1995); CSA (Csárkvar), Kretzoi (1942); POL (Polgardi 2) [planned for 2/3 of a whole page width]

151x188mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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FIGURE 5. Relationships between lengths (L) and widths (W) of lower dentition in *Eomellivora*. Legend and Source, the same of figure 4. [planned for 2/3 of a whole page width]
77x49mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 6. Main comparative material of species of *Eomellivora* recognized in this paper. A1, MNHN-TRQ-1005, *Eomellivora piveteaui* from Yassiören (YAS), occlusal view of maxilla fragment with P4 and M1; A2, MNHN-TRQ-1004, lectotype of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from YAS, lateral view of mandible fragment; A3, MNHN-TRQ-1004 occlusal view; B1, PMU-M3692, holotype of *Eomellivora wimani* from Shangyingou (SH), lateral view of skull fragment with complete upper dentition; B2, PMU-M3692, ventral view; B3, PMU-M3693, holotype of *Eomellivora wimani* from SH, lateral view of mandible fragment with complete lower dentition; B4, PMU-M3693, occlusal view; C1, PIN-No. 268 holotype of *Eomellivora ursogulo* from Grebeniki (GRE), occlusal view; C2, PIN-No. 269a, holotype of *Eomellivora ursogulo* from GRE, lateral view of mandible with complete lower dentition; C3, PIN-No. 269a, occlusal view; D1, MFGI-Ob-2676, holotype of *Eomellivora hungarica* from Polgardi 2 (POL), lateral view of mandible with fragmentary p3, p4 and m1; D2, MFGI-Ob-2676, occlusal view. Scale bar equals 5 cm. [planned for page width] 214x252mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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FIGURE 7. A, Chronostratigraphic position of the fossil localities where *Eomellivora* are found, according to, Tobien, (1955); Ginsburg et al., (1981); Wolsan and Semenov, (1996); Lunkka et al., (1999); Semenov, (2001); Morlo and Semenov, (2004); Tedford et al., (2004); Morales and Pickford (2005), Nargolwalla et al., (2006); Kováč et al. (2006); Morales et al., (2008); Zhu et al., (2008); Hír and Kökay, (2010); Woodburne, (2010); Lungu and Rzebik-Kowalska, (2011); Koufos, (2012); Kaakinen et al., (2013); Vangengeim and Tesakov, (2013); B, Calibrated hypothesis phylogenetic based on Appendix 1–2 (see figure 9 for more details). [planned for page width]
173x166mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 8. Ratio diagram of all Eomellivora described in the bibliography. The dental measurements of *Gulo gulo* B.1280 serve as the standard for comparison (solid line at Y axis equal to 100) Legend and Source, the same of figure 4. [planned for 2/3 of a whole page width] 216x400mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 9. Phylogenetic relationships of *Eomellivora piveteau* within Musteloidea (Carnivora). A Bootstrap tree (98 steps; CI = 0.4592; HI= 0.5408; RI=0,3977) has been obtained by means of PAUP*4.0b10 (Swofford, 2002). The outgroup was *Canis lupus* (Linnaeus, 1758). Character/taxa matrix is detailed in the Appendix 1-2. Apomorphic characters supporting each node: Node A: 2 (1); 8 (1); 9 (1); 10 (1); 13 (1); 15 (1); 31 (1); 37 (1); 38 (1); 40 (1); 42 (1); Node B: 7(1); 20 (1); 21 (1); 22 (1); 39 (1); 41 (1), 43 (1); Node C: 4 (1); 5 (1); 6 (1); 11 (1); 14 (1); 25 (1); 28 (2); 30 (1); 33 (1).
62x44mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 10. Sequential reconstruction of the head of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from Batallones in lateral view. A, life appearance; B, reconstructed skull and mandible; Skull and mandible BAT-3 '09.1000. Artwork by Adam Hartstone-Rose. [planned for page width]
228x285mm (300 x 300 DPI)

TABLE 1. Upper tooth measurements (in mm) of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from
Batallones localities.

	I3		CX		P2		P3		P4		M1	
	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W
BAT-3'09. 1000 (left)	—	—	—	—	8.7	5.9	14.5	10.5	21.3	—	11.6	22.1
BAT-3'09. 1000 (right)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	21.2	14.2 ca	10.9	20.5
BAT-3'13. 185 (left)	—	—	—	—	7.7	5.1	13.1	8.3	21.3	15.4	10.8	18.3
BAT-3'13. 185 (right)	—	—	—	—	7.8	5.2	12.9	8.4	21.4	14.8	10.5	19.1
BAT-3'09. 688	7.2	5.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
BAT-3'08. 635	—	—	13.4	10.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
BAT-10-08-G4-102	—	—	—	—	7.7	5.1	—	—	—	—	—	—
BAT-3'09. 250	—	—	—	—	—	—	13.3	8.1	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2. Lower tooth measurements (in mm) of *Eomellivora piveteaui* from Batallones localities.

	c1		p2		p3		p4		m1		m2	
	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W
BAT-3'08. 526	12.0	9.3	8.2	4.7	10.7	7.3	14.8	7.6	23.1	8.3	—	—
BAT-3'09. 1000 (left)	—	—	8.2	5.3	11.8	8.4	15.8	8.8	24.5	9.4	6.9	4.9
BAT-3'09. 1000 (right)	—	—	8.3	5.5	11.8	8.3	16.1	8.7	24.1	—	—	—
BAT-3'13. 230	—	—	—	—	—	—	15.4	8.2	23.2	9.2	—	—
BAT-3'11. 1180	—	—	—	—	—	—	13.7	7.3	—	—	—	—
BAT-3'09. 2a	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	19.7	8.5	—	—
BAT-3'12. 1086	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	22.2	8.1 ca.	—	—
BAT-10'12-G2-4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	20.6	8.6	7.3 ca	5.8

TABLE 3. Taxonomic concordance of *Eomellivora*.

Locality	MN zones	Original taxon/ Author	Wolsan and Semenov (1996)	This paper
Ngogora (Kenya)	MN8	<i>Eomellivora tugenensis</i> / Morales and Pickford (2005)	—	<i>Eomellivora tugenensis</i>
Yassiören (Turkey)	MN9	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i> / Ozansoy (1965)	<i>Eomellivora wimani piveteaui</i>	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i>
Wissberg (Germany)	MN9	Mellivorine gen. et sp. indet / Tobien (1955)	—	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i>
Kalfa (Moldova)	MN9	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i> / Lungu (1978)	<i>Eomellivora wimani piveteaui</i>	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i>
Los Valles de Fuentidueña (Spain)	MN9	<i>Eomellivora liguritor</i> / Crusafont-Pairó and Ginsburg (1973)	<i>Eomellivora wimani piveteaui</i>	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i>
Gritsev (Ukraine)	MN9	<i>Eomellivora wimani piveteaui</i> / Wolsan and Semenov (1996)	<i>Eomellivora wimani piveteaui</i>	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>
Borský Svätý Jur (Slovakia)	MN9	<i>Perunium ursogulo</i> / Lupták (1995)	—	<i>Eomellivora sp</i>
Batallones-3 and 10 (Spain)	MN10	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i> / Valenciano et al.,(2012)	—	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i>
Ravin de la Pluie (Greece)	MN10	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i> / Koufos (2012)	—	<i>Eomellivora piveteaui</i>
Grebeniki (Ukraine)	MN11	<i>Perunium ursogulo</i> / Orlov (1948)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora ursogulo</i>
Csákvar (Hungary)	MN11	<i>Eomellivora hungarica altera</i> / Kretzoi (1942)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora sp</i>
Novaya Emetovka (Ukraine)	MN12	<i>Eomellivora aff. wimani</i> / Orlov (1948)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>
Györszentmárton 2 (Hungary)	MN12	<i>Eomellivora orlovi</i> / Kretzoi (1965)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>
Cimislia (Moldova)	MN12	<i>Eomellivora rumana</i> / Simionescu (1938)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>
Liuwangou + Shangyingou (China)	MN12–13	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i> Zdansky (1924)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>
Kern River Formation site 50 (California, USA)	MN12–13	<i>Eomellivora cf. wimani</i> / Stock and Hall (1933)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>
Polgardi 2 (Hungary)	MN13	<i>Eomellivora hungarica</i> / Kretzoi (1942)	<i>Eomellivora wimani wimani</i>	<i>Eomellivora hungarica</i>